

How to Run the Notebooks

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1 Steps to run data generation

- The scripts `data_generator.py`, `data_generator_a1.py` and `data_generator_a2.py` define the classes for the data generators.
- Run `data_generation-A1.py` to generate the dataset for research question **RQ1**.
- Run `data_generation-A2.py` to generate the dataset for research question **RQ2**.

2 Steps to run score analysis

- The scripts `score_analyser.py` defines the class used for all the analyses.
- Each analysis notebook is labelled **analysis_{Research Question}_{Perspective}_{Score}** corresponding to the research question being answered, the perspective and the aggregate score under analysis.
- Additionally, analysis notebooks labelled **analysis_{Research Question}_{Perspective}_{Score}_merged_search** contain the merged grid search across version flakiness formulae.
- Analysis notebooks labelled **analysis_{Research Question}_{Score}** contain the merged grid search across perspectives.

Figure 1: Grid Search Flow Chart

- For research question 2, (**RQ2**), analysis notebooks labelled **analysis_{Research Question}_{Perspective}_{Score}_cc** should be executed **first** to generate the Fréchet distance data for all the tests.
- For research question 2, (**RQ2**), a number is appended to the files to indicate the number of days of history used to calculate the scores since, for each length, we must also include the λ values in our grid search.
- Figure 1 shows the order in which to execute the analysis files. All files from the previous level should be executed before proceeding.

3 Notebooks directory contents

General Scripts and Files

- constants.py
- input_configuration.py
- logger.py
- message_strings.py
- requirements.txt
- utilities.py

Data Generation Scripts

- data_generation-A1.py
- data_generation-A2.py
- data_generator.py - Base class for all data generators.
- data_generator_a1.py - A1 Data Generator class.
- data_generator_a2.py - A2 Data Generator class.

Flakiness Quantifier Tool Runner Scripts

- flakiness_quantifier.py - Base class used to configure how to run the flakiness quantifier tool.
- flakiness_quantification_RQ1.py
- flakiness_quantification_RQ2.py

Analysis Notebooks and Scripts

Keys

- **RQ1** - Research Question 1
- **RQ2** - Research Question 2
- **PIW** - Prospectively Increasing Window
- **RIW** - Retrospectively Increasing Window
- **u** - Unweighted Flakiness Score
- **w** - Weighted Flakiness Score

- **cc** - Curve Comparison

Files

- score_analyser.py - Base class for all analysis.
- analysis_RQ1_piwi_u.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_piwi_u_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_piwi_w.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_piwi_w_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_rwi_u.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_rwi_u_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_rwi_w.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_rwi_w_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_u_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ1_w_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_u.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_u_cc.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_u_cc_confidence.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_u_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_1.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_2.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_4.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_8.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_16.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_32.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_64.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_cc.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piwi_w_cc_confidence.ipynb

- analysis_RQ2_piw_w_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_piw_w_s.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_u.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_u_cc.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_u_cc_confidence.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_u_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_1.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_2.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_4.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_8.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_16.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_32.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_64.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_cc.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_cc_confidence.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_riw_w_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_u_merged_search.ipynb
- analysis_RQ2_w_merged_search.ipynb